

In-depth interview Protocol

Dimensions	Questions
Demographic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What type of tourism business do you operate? • How many years have you been in operation? • How many employees do you currently have? • What is your approximate annual revenue/omzet? • What is your role in the business?
Resource Constraint Experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What kinds of resource limitations have you experienced in your business? (Probes: financial capital, materials, equipment, infrastructure, skilled labor, formal business support) • Could you describe a specific situation where you faced significant resource constraints? What happened and how did you respond? • How did you feel when initially confronted with these limitations? • Has your perception of these constraints changed over time? If so, how?
Bricolage Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When faced with limited resources, how do you typically create solutions? • Could you share an example of how you've creatively used available resources to overcome limitations? • How do you decide which resources to use and how to combine them when standard resources aren't available? • Do you collaborate with others when resources are limited? If so, how does this process work?
Value and Meaning Construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What aspects of your work are most meaningful to you despite resource limitations? • Has working with limited resources affected how you view yourself as an entrepreneur? In what ways? • Do you see any positive aspects or opportunities that have emerged from the resource constraints you've faced?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <input type="checkbox"/> How does your approach to resource limitations connect to your personal or cultural values?
Cultural Identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does your cultural background influence how you respond to resource constraints? • Are there specific cultural values or traditions that guide your approach to resource limitations? • How does being a tourism entrepreneur in Yogyakarta specifically shape your experience with resource constraints? • Do you feel your business practices help preserve cultural heritage? In what ways?
Social Connection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do resource constraints affect your relationships with others in your community? • When you find creative solutions to resource limitations, how do others (customers, community members, other entrepreneurs) respond? • Has your approach to resource constraints strengthened your connection to any particular groups or communities? How? • Do you share knowledge or resources with other entrepreneurs facing similar constraints?
Psychological Well-being	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do you maintain motivation and positive outlook when facing resource limitations? • What strategies help you manage stress related to resource constraints? • Have your experiences with resource constraints affected your confidence or sense of capability? In what ways? • What gives you a sense of pride or accomplishment in your work despite limitations?
Closing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What advice would you give to other entrepreneurs facing similar resource constraints? • Is there anything else about your experience with resource constraints

	that you think is important for us to understand?
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Observation Protocol

Focus Area	Elements to Observe
Physical Environment & Resource Utilization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available resources and organization • Resource repurposing/combinations • Space utilization and adaptation • Evidence of traditional techniques • Signs of "making do"
Social Interactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Owner/employee interactions • Customer interactions • Community connections • Resource sharing practices • Communication about constraints
Psychological Responses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emotional expressions • Decision-making processes • Problem-solving approaches • Pride/frustration indicators • Constraint discussions
Cultural Elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural symbols/practices • Value expressions • Heritage references • Identity markers • Community traditions

Post Observation Checklist

Task	Completed
Field notes completed immediately after session	
Notes reviewed for completeness and clarity	
Preliminary themes and patterns identified	
Connections to interview data noted	
Follow-up questions prepared	
Field notes shared with research team	

Ethical Considerations

Dimensions	Checklist
Participant confidentiality maintained	
Observation conducted with explicit prior consent	
Avoided making judgments about observed practices	
Discontinued observation if it caused discomfort	
Provided opportunity for participant feedback	

